

Forecasting Peak and appliance level demand using Smart meter data

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Abstract:

The smart grid is an important component of smart technology. Smart grid technology enables two-way communication between the energy consumer and the energy distributor. Smart meters which are installed at the consumer side acts as the bridge between the consumer and the grid. Data analytics can be applied to the data collected by the smart meter to forecast electricity consumption. The forecast will help the energy providers to manage energy distribution effectively as the demand is known in advance. Appliance level data analytics can predict the usage of electricity at the level of appliance consumption. With this prediction, users can decide on the usage of appliances to manage electricity consumption and hence reduce the bill. In this paper, a machine learning model using the support vector machine is used to predict consumer's electricity peak demand usage, and a hybrid model comprising multilayer perceptron with k-means is built to predict maximum electricity consumption at the appliance level.

The proposed SVM model performs better than the univariate ARIMA model by considering external features that affect electricity consumption. The hybrid MLP model with k-means clustering performs at accuracy in the range 84-99%.

I. INTRODUCTION

Since the early 2000, many countries are moving towards smart energy management technology. Digitization and decarbonization are the pathways for future energy and power systems. Smart grid is a cyber-physical-social system that enables to couple power, customers, and distributors [1-3]. Smart grids have revolutionized smart energy management systems which can be seen by the increase in the deployment of smart meters across the globe over the past decade. Smart meters alongside communication network and data management system forms the advanced metering infrastructure (AMI), which helps the power delivery system by recording the consumer load profiles and facilitates the bi-directional flow of data. There are 5 main players in the smart power system: retailers, aggregators, distributors, consumers and, data service providers. In the future market, individual load forecasting inputs the electricity usage from the home energy management systems and provides forecasting that not only helps in contributing to transactive energy among consumers, but also to reduce the electricity bills. A lot of research is going on load forecasting using smart meter data in recent days to contribute to efficient power management systems[4]. Many Countries have started the transformation from energy to smart energy. The "Grid 2030" strategy is implemented by the US Department of Energy for the American electrical system. Statistical tools and machine learning models are gaining a lot of popularity to obtain real-time predictions. Power companies are switching from

reactive to proactive maintenance on the smart meter data by applying Machine learning algorithms to predict the MTTF/MTBF [5].

Load forecasting is crucial for electricity management (generation, transmission, and distribution). Load forecasting is done not only at different scales like meter level, integrated load level, and commercial buildings level but also at different horizons such as very short term, short term, medium-term, and long term[6]. The need for short-term load forecasting at low voltage levels is gaining a lot of importance because the electricity network is moving towards a low carbon future. Stephan et al. compare the different methods like kernel density method, linear regression, and autoregressive methods used for load forecasting on low voltage feeders with and without the impact of climatic conditions like temperature [7].

Load forecasting is also affected by structural and behavioral determinants which affect electricity consumption. Weather, location of the building, and flood area are considered as the important determinants, and income level, building age, and ownership are considered as the least significant determinants [8]. A non-linear mixed-effects model is proposed in [9] to capture the impact of additional variables which may influence energy usage.

Demand forecasting is the most important component of the supply chain as it can estimate the consumer demands for the future. If the demand management is not done by the organization the whole supply chain is affected. An ensemble model is proposed in [10] with minimal variation inaccuracy. Even though several methods have evolved to forecast the smart meter data not all consider the inherent uncertainty on the demand side. The load forecast must be coherent in the sense the aggregated series should be the sum of individual disaggregated series [11-13]. A hierarchical probabilistic forecasting method is proposed in [14] which uses random sampling and a mean forecasting approach for coherent forecast distribution.

Algorithms built for power demand forecasting must not only be able to predict the load variations with less error rate but must also capture sudden changes in the power pattern. Machine learning algorithms are applied to the smart meter data not only for load forecasting but also to inspect the power theft and predicting the prices for the electricity for the next day.

Load forecasting is done mostly using algorithms like SVM, ANN, and statistical models like ARIMA[15,16]. The machine learning algorithms built for power demand forecasting must not only be able to predict the load variations with less error rate but also capture the sudden changes in the power pattern. A deep CNN model with LSTM load forecasting is proposed in [17] which enables automatic controlling of appliances and avoids energy wastage that occurs because of the lifestyle of the home users. Nivethitha et al. proposed an energy forecasting model using long-short term memory networks with improved sine and cosine optimization algorithms for forecasting energy consumptions of buildings smart meter data [18]. Building characteristics are also important to make policies and decisions on electricity consumption as the impact of certain characteristics may increase or decrease electricity consumption. A mixed-effect model which can capture the correlation between the identified parameters on the population is proposed in [19]. Machine learning models like Extreme Gradient boosting (XGBoost), Categorical boosting, and light gradient boosting are applied on smart meter data to inspect the power theft problems which can cause a huge financial loss for the utility providers [20]. ANN models can also be applied to the price profiles for the electricity to identify the market price patterns which can help the retailers increase their profits [21].

In order to benefit energy management, we propose an Artificial intelligence-based model which monitors the energy consumption at the appliance level and also forecasts peak electricity demand of individual home by considering the history of consumption and external factors.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed artificial intelligent model forecasts peak electric energy consumption and predicts appliances that consume maximum electricity. The models are built using machine learning algorithm support vector machine for forecasting peak consumer demand and a hybrid model comprising MLP with K-means to predict appliance level consumption. The model is given with inputs which are time-series data of electricity consumption and external factors such as temperature and day of the week. The data is collected from a smart meter which is installed at the consumer side.

A. Support Vector Machine(SVM)

SVM is a simple, flexible machine learning model which supports supervised learning. SVM supports solutions to both regression and classification problems. SVM that supports regression will have the below features.

Kernel: This function transforms linearly inseparable input features to separable high dimensional feature space. The transformed space is separable by a plane.

Hyperplane: It is a best-fit plane that fits the input data.

Decision boundary: This determines the vectors that are close to the hyperplane.

Support Vectors: feature vectors that are very close to the hyperplane.

SVM model can be defined mathematically as in equation (1)

$$G(t) = W^T\phi(t) + b \quad (1)$$

Where,

$G(t)$: Predicted output value.

W^T : Vector of Weights.

$\phi(t)$: High dimensional feature space derived from input space.

b : Bias.

SVM supports different kernel functions such as linear, polynomial, and radial kernels to form a best fit hyperplane. Weights and bias are adjusted to maximize the hyperplane.

The proposed forecasting system takes combined input features that include electric usage, weather data, and day of the week. All the input features are of integer data. Before training the model a window of historical consumption is formed. This window contains previous consumption values for a period of 12 hours. The input is divided into a training set and validation set. Using the training set the SVM model is trained to predict future consumption. A validation set is used to verify the fitness of the SVM model using the R2 score.

Input: Input Dataset(D) with input features and numeric target values.

- From the Input Dataset(D) add 12 new columns as a feature which is a window of previous electricity consumption for a period of the previous 12 hours.

- For each row in the Input Dataset(D), perform scaling of each column to have a standard deviation of one.
- Divide the Input Dataset(D) into two parts TrainSet(T) and ValidationSet(V)
- Select an SVM model with a specific kernel.
- Train the selected SVM model with TrainSet(T)
- Predict the peak electricity demand on the ValidationSet(V) using the previously built model.
- Evaluate the model using R2 score on predicted value and actual value.
- Retrain the SVM model if model performance is less than the ARIMA model.

B. Multi-layer Perceptron(MLP) with K-means

A Multilayer Perceptron is a class of artificial neural networks that has one or more hidden layers. The multilayer perceptron is an interconnection of neurons across the different layers. There are three main layers in a multilayer perceptron namely the input layer, hidden layer, and output layer. The input to the model is provided through the input layer, passed on through the hidden layers consisting of activation functions to perform the classification and the final output is seen at the output layer. Figure 1 shows the structure of a multilayer perceptron with many inputs and a single output.

Figure 1. Structure of perceptron [23]

Multilayer perceptron algorithm learns a function as shown in equation (2)

$$f(.) : R^m \rightarrow R^o \quad (2)$$

by training on a dataset, with 'm' dimensional input and an 'o' dimensional output with a feature set of the form $X = x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m$ and a target function y . A non-linear activation function is used to capture the non-linearity in the input. The bias and weights are adjusted in the model for the feature extraction. The layers determine the precision of the model output.

Mathematically after including the weight and bias MLP can be represented as in equation (3)

$$f(.) = A(b^{(2)} + M^{(2)}(B(b^{(1)} + M^{(1)}x))) \quad (3)$$

Where,

f: Function that maps input to output ($R^m \rightarrow R^o$) size of input and output vector being m and o respectively.

A, B: Activation functions

$b^{(1)}$, $b^{(2)}$: Bias

$M^{(1)}$, $M^{(2)}$: Weight matrices

The hybrid model is constructed as a combination of k-means clustering which is an unsupervised algorithm. The data points with similar levels of electricity consumption are clustered which can thus narrow down the window for the prediction using the MLP algorithm. The model produces a parallel output of all the appliances. As the usage of an appliance in daily living is also correlated and not all the appliances run together, the clustering of the appliances determines the correlation between the daily usage of various appliances.

Input: Dataset(D) with features(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) representing appliance level consumptions.

Output: Target values($p(x_1), p(x_2), \dots, p(x_n)$) showing the predictions for all features.

- Cluster index(k) is set to 3.
- Determine the initial cluster means m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 .
- Until no change is observed,
 - For every value in the dataset
 - Find the Euclidean distance between the value and cluster mean.
 - Assign the value to the cluster with the minimum distance.
 - end for.
- end until
- For every value add a new feature indicating the cluster label
 - Pick a suitable cluster from the set of clusters created
 - New dataset(D) has data records corresponding to the selected cluster.
 - Build a historic window for 5 hours on the train set (X, y) and validation set (X', y').
 - Build the Multi-Layer Perceptron model with n-inputs, 1-Dense layer, and n-output layers for each input feature.
 - Select the loss function to evaluate the model and optimization the model parameters
 - for all the values in the train set(X, y):
 - Fit the previously built model.
- end for.
- Validate the model on the validation set(X', y').
- Model performance is evaluated using the loss function.

C. System Architecture and Design

The proposed system is fed with time series data which is captured by the smart meter. This input time series data has features comprising electricity consumption of different houses in an apartment, electricity consumption of individual appliances used at each house, and weather-related data which is specific to the apartment's geographical location.

Statistical algorithm Auto Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) is used to forecast peak electricity consumption by the individual home. The ARIMA model is considered as a Null model on which SVM outperforms in the prediction of peak demand. Machine learning algorithm Support Vector Machine (SVM) is applied on the input data set for predicting peak electricity demand. R2 score [22] used as the metric to compare results from the two different models. R2 is a statistical evaluation metric that is used to find the goodness of fit of a model. The metric values range from 0 to 1. An R2 score of 1 implies the regression predictions perfectly fit the data. If the R2 score of SVM model is more than ARIMA model, then it is concluded that the proposed model performs better than the Null model. The hybrid Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) algorithm with k-means clustering is applied on the input dataset. This model forecasts electricity consumption of individual appliance for the coming.

The proposed system's process is divided into three major phases (Figure 2):

➤ **Dataset Loading:**

- Time series data set is fed to the model as input.
- The data set is taken from UMass Trace Repository. The Repository provides network, storage, and other traces to the research community for analysis.
- The UMass Smart Data set has two sub-datasets namely the Weather dataset and the Electrical dataset.
- Electrical data set is used to forecast peak demand of electricity. This data set consists of minute-wise electricity consumption from an apartment.
- Electrical data also consists of electricity consumption at the appliance level from each home captured at the rate of a minute. This data set is used for forecasting electricity consumption at the appliance level.
- The weather data set provides the seasonal weather conditions of the physical location where the apartment is situated.

➤ **Data Pre-processing:**

- Once the dataset is loaded in the Data load phase, it is important to pre-process the data before it is used for training models.
- In the pre-processing phase the whole data set is parsed through to find any missing values and anomalies that would bring down the model accuracy.
- Missing values observed in the electricity consumption column are filled with the average value of hourly electricity consumption.
- After the dataset is free from all the missing values all the data points are scaled-down. Scaling ensured that the range of feature values lies between 0 and 1.
- Before feeding the input to the model building phase, create a historical window of the previous consumption,

Figure 2. System architecture of the proposed system

➤ **Model Training and Evaluation:**

- After Pre-processing, the data is fed further to build the model.
- The SVM model is trained on the input dataset to forecast the user's peak electricity demand for the coming week.
- R2 score from SVM model is calculated and compared with the Null model. In case the R2 score is below the level of the Null model, SVM model parameters are tuned until the model performs better than the R2 score of the Null model.
- The hybrid model comprising MLP with K-means is applied to the input data to forecast the consumption level of the top five appliances for the coming week in a house.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP AND DATA ANALYSIS:

Umass Trace repository provides a smart meter dataset intending to optimize electricity consumption at the home level. The time-series data set is collected from real scenarios and includes around 400 homes. This also provides information on the weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, etc. The electrical data set from the Smart meter of each house has a feature 'consumption' which captures usage of electricity with an interval of one minute. The length of the dataset is 503760. The weather data set includes weather conditions such as temperature, humidity, etc. captured every hour for a period of one year. To forecast electricity consumption using SVM model, the two datasets are combined by taking consumption and temperature features from the electrical data set and the

weather data set respectively. Appliance level data set is a time series dataset that includes electricity consumption by different appliances used in a home. This data set has 13 unique features and is of length 246639 captured at a rate of 1 minute. From this data set 5 top appliances are considered based on their energy consumption level for predicting the appliance level consumption model which is build using MLP with K-means algorithm. All the data set are preprocessed before using them for training the model. The huge data set is aggregated to hourly consumption. All the missing values are filled with the hourly mean. The models are validated using R2 score. The R2 score is a statistical measure that calculates the closeness of the predicted value by the model to the actual value. R2 score value lies in the range 0 and 1.

TABLE 1
COMPARISON OF PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF PROPOSED MODEL WITH SVM AND ARIMA

Algorithm	SVM kernel			ARIMA
Apartment ID	Radial kernel	Linear kernel	Polynomial kernel	
Apt1	88	87	80	83.5
Apt2	80	80	74	74
Apt3	73	72	73	70

The proposed SVM model forecasts electricity consumption for the coming week. The accuracy of the SVM model is found to be between 72-88%. The univariate model ARIMA has an accuracy in the range of 70-84%. The predicted values of SVM are better compared with the univariate ARIMA model. The SVM model has performed better by capturing the variation in electricity consumption with respect to the previous usage window as well as an external condition like temperature and day of the week.

Figure 3. Result plot of the proposed SVM system

The 7 days forecast value from the SVM model is plotted (Figure 3). X-axis represents the electricity usage and Y-axis represents the 7 days frame for which the values are predicted. Even though ARIMA and SVM capture the variation in electricity usage effectively, from the comparison of scores from both the models it can be inferred SVM forecasts better than ARIMA because that electricity consumption prediction depends not only on the history of consumption but also on external factors such as temperature and day of the week.

TABLE 2
PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MLP WITH K-MEANS

Method	Outlets	Furnace	DuctHeater	Washing Machine	DishWasher
MLP with clustering	99	84	99	98	91
MLP without clustering	89	79	88	92	96

MLP with clustering and without clustering is used to predict the top 5 appliances with maximum consumption for the next 7 days. The accuracy of the proposed hybrid MLP model with clustering and simple MLP model is captured in Table 2. In the hybrid model clustering enhances the accuracy by combining the appliances which are interrelated in their consumption level.

IV. CONCLUSION

The proposed machine learning model with the SVM algorithm is simple and effectively forecasts the electricity consumption of a home in an apartment for the next 7 days. The SVM model can produce better precision by considering external factors like temperature, day of the week which impact the electricity consumption. From the comparison of SVM and Null model's performance, it is concluded that electricity consumption is greatly affected by external factors as well as previous history of consumption. The proposed hybrid MLP with K-means clustering model can effectively be used to monitor and manage the electricity consumptions of individual electric appliances. Clustering determines the pattern of electricity consumption by different appliances thereby increases the performance of the MLP model. The proposed model can be enhanced by studying other factors that would cause variation in the electricity consumption and considering those features for forecasting. Some of the external factors which impact consumption are the number of residents, windspeed and humidity.

REFERENCES

- [1] D. Alahakoon and X. Yu, Smart electricity meters data intelligence and future energy systems: A Survey, *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, Vol. 12, pp. 425-436, Feb. 2016.
- [2] J. Zheng, D. W. Gao and L. Lin, Smart Meters in Smart Grid: An Overview, Denver: IEEE Conference. 2013 IEEE Green Technologies Conference (GreenTech), pp. 57-64, 2013.
- [3] B. Subhash and V Rajagopal, Overview of smart metering system in Smart Grid scenario. Bangalore: IEEE conference. 2014 Power and energy systems; Towards Sustainable energy, pp. 1-6, 2014.
- [4] Wang Yi, Chen Qixin, Kang Chongqing, Overview of Smart Meter Data Analytics, *Smart Meter Data Analytics: Electricity Consumer Behavior Modeling, Aggregation, and Forecasting*, Springer Singapore, 2020.
- [5] C. Rudin et al., Machine Learning for the New York City Power Grid, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, Vol. 34, no. 2, Feb 2012.
- [6] Elham M. Eskandarnia, Sameem Abdul Kareem, Hesham M. Al-Ammal, A Review of Smart Meter Load Forecasting Techniques: Scale and Horizon, *International Conference on Information Society and Smart Cities ICS2018At: Cambridge, UK, 2018.*

- [7] Haben, Stephen and Giasemidis, Georgios and Ziel, Florian and Arora, Siddharth, Short term load forecasting and the effect of temperature at the low voltage level, *International Journal of Forecasting*, Vol.35, pp. 1469–1484, 2019.
- [8] Amir Kavousian, Ram Rajagopal, Martin Fischer, Determinants of residential electricity consumption: Using smart meter data to examine the effect of climate, building characteristics, appliance stock, and occupants' behavior, *Energy*, Vol 55, pp. 184-194, 2013.
- [9] Cameron Roach, Rob Hyndman, Souhaib Ben Taieb, Non-linear mixed-effects models for time series forecasting of smart meter demand, research publication at Monash university, Oct 2020.
- [10] Adhikari N.C.D, Smys S, Bestak R, Chen JZ, Kotuliak I, An Intelligent Approach to Demand Forecasting, *International Conference on Computer Networks and Communication Technologies*, vol 15, pp 167-183, Springer, Singapore, 2018.
- [11] Cameron Roach, “Reconciled boosted models for GEFCom2017 hierarchical probabilistic load forecasting”, *International Journal of Forecasting*, vol.35,issue.4, pp.1439-1450, 2019.
- [12] P. Amin, L. Cherkasova, R. Aitken and V. Kache, Automating Energy Demand Modeling and Forecasting Using Smart Meter Data, 2019 IEEE International Congress on Internet of Things (ICIOT), Milan, Italy, 2019, pp. 133-137, 2019.
- [13] X. Sun et al., An Efficient Approach to Short-Term Load Forecasting at the Distribution Level, in *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 2526-2537, July 2016.
- [14] Taieb S.B., Taylor J.W., Hyndman R.J., Hierarchical Probabilistic Forecasting of Electricity Demand With Smart Meter Data, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 116 (533) , pp. 27-43, 2021.
- [15] Choi, Cho, and Kim, Power Demand Forecasting using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Deep-Learning Model for Monitoring Energy Sustainability, *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 3, p. 1109, Feb. 2020.
- [16] Dudek, G. Multilayer perceptron for short-term load forecasting: from global to local approach, *Neural Computer & Application*, vol.32, pp. 3695–3707, 2020.
- [17] M. Khan, J. Seo, and D. Kim, Towards Energy Efficient Home Automation: A Deep Learning Approach, *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 24, p. 7187, Dec. 2020.
- [18] Nivethitha Somu, Gauthama Raman M R, Krithi Ramamritham, “A hybrid model for building energy consumption forecasting using long short term memory networks”, *Applied Energy*, vol.261, pp.114-131,2020.
- [19] Cameron Roach, Estimating electricity impact profiles for building characteristics using smart meter data and mixed models, *Energy & Buildings*, vol.211,2019.
- [20] Prof. Rohit Bamane, Mervyn Vinod, Jahnavi Shah, Shweta Ahuja, Aditya Sahariya, Smart Meter for Power Theft Detection using Machine Learning, *International Journal of Scientific Research and Engineering Development*, vol.3, pp.526-528, 2020.
- [21] Ioannis P. Panapakidis, Athanasios S. Dagoumas, Day-ahead electricity price forecasting via the application of artificial neural network based models, *Applied Energy*, vol.172, pp.132-151, 2016.
- [22] S. Aman, Y. Simmhan and V. K. Prasanna, Holistic Measures for Evaluating Prediction Models in Smart Grids, *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, Vol.27. pp. 475-488, Feb 2015
- [23] Online resource : 1.17. Neural network models (supervised) — scikit-learn 0.24.1 documentation (scikit-learn.org) accessed on 24.03.2021